

Who Drives the Societal Role of Universities? Researcher Agency and Bottom-Up Regional Engagement in a Peripheral Region

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Abstract

This paper aims to understand the factors that determine the societal role of higher education institutions (HEIs) in peripheral regions characterised by the prevalence of thin regional innovation systems. Our analysis of existing literature suggests that HEIs develop a regional profile in response to an exogenous factor, namely peripherality, through endogenous factors such as HEI orientation and TM strategy. We conducted a case study applying mixed methodologies, including a quantitative survey and in-depth semi-structured qualitative interviews. Our results show that universities can overcome limitations related to peripherality by developing a regional profile that adapts to regional needs with an orientation towards applied sciences. Interestingly, the development of this profile does not necessarily depend on top-down policy decisions taken by HEI strategic leaders. On the contrary, our case study shows that it is driven by researchers through their personal contacts and networks.

Keywords: Higher Education Institutions (HEIs); Universities; Societal Contribution; Third Mission; Thin Innovation Systems; Peripheral Regions; Sustainable Entrepreneurial Universities; Applied Sciences.

1. Introduction

There is consensus with respect to the fact that the physical presence of a university in a given region is necessary but not a sufficient condition for economic development to occur (Pinheiro et al. 2017, Compagnucci and Spigarelli 2020). Given their heterogeneous specificities, regions respond differently to development policies and, consequently, the role of universities in core economic hubs does not necessarily has similar effects in peripheral or thin regions (Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022, Benneworth 2018, Pinheiro et al. 2017). The growing literature focusing on the regional role of HEIs indicates that the regional impact of university knowledge depends on internal corporate factors – such as entrepreneurial culture – and external factors at the regional level (Bonaccorsi 2017, Sanchez-Barrioluengo and Benneworth 2019, Guerrero et al. 2024). In this vein, peripheral regions are considered to be relatively disadvantaged when it comes to

innovation performance compared to urban regions which are seen to be home to more R&D activity, to have more innovative firms, to have better skills and infrastructure, and to benefit from more developed networks, connectivity and proximity (Eder 2019, Eder and Tripl 2019, Glücker et al. 2023). Contrarily, cities have been considered in the literature as innovation machines (Florida et al. 2017).

Thus, there is a majority of studies that support the idea that universities in peripheries have a less significant contribution to regional development (Cai and Ahmad 2023, Kohoutek et al. 2017). They argue that universities in peripheral regions experience barriers that undermine their societal role (Kohoutek et al. 2017, Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022, Cai and Ahmad 2023). Nevertheless, there are recent studies that show that universities can adopt new roles in their third mission strategy that may present opportunities for peripheral areas that lack the innovation attributes of leading regions (Delbridge et al. 2025). Hence, the empirical evidence regarding the societal contribution of universities in peripheral regions remains limited and inconclusive (Kohoutek et al. 2017, Compagnucci and Spigarelli 2020) and therefore the effect of peripherality is far from clear.

Therefore, further empirical evidence could contribute to clarify how HEIs develop their societal mission in peripheral regions and how this is affected by the evolving role of HEIs. Indeed, important efforts have been done in clarifying the new role of universities in regional development at the theoretical level (Cai and Ahmad 2023, Guerrero et al. 2024). Nevertheless, a systematic empirical analysis about transformations of HEIs through this lens is still lacking (Cai and Ahmad 2023). In the same vein, there has been a call for, on the one hand, empirically re-viewing the participation of universities in the innovation ecosystem, especially in response to the new socio-economic paradigm (Guerrero et al. 2024); and, on the other hand, to focus on specific cases and how universities develop their TM strategy in response to the socioeconomic environment in which they operate (Compagnucci and Spigarelli 2020).

When focusing on the role of universities in peripheral regions, a set of questions remain unresolved: How does periphery matter regarding social engagement of the university? How does the different orientation of the university influence its contribution to regional development? In this sense, does the emerging societal role of the university in innovation ecosystems facilitate that universities in peripheral regions contribute to regional development?

The objective of our research is to provide a clearer empirical understanding of how universities develop their societal contribution within the context of a peripheral region. We aim to understand to what extent the universities' societal role is endogenously decided by the university – according to its orientation and their TM strategy – or is rather determined by exogenous factors – such as its embeddedness in a peripheral region.

We argue that universities develop their societal role according to the university's orientation and their TM strategy –endogenous factors; nevertheless, third mission is also a response to the local context and the needs of the regional stakeholders (Compagnucci and Spigarelli 2020, Göransson et al. 2009); therefore, the characteristics of the ecosystem – peripherality – will be an exogenous factor influencing HEIs' societal role. Therefore, we argue that HEI's societal contribution would be the response to these factors that evolve together and jointly influence each other, creating an evolutionary trajectory that is specific to each university. We suggest that when a HEI's societal role has evolved to respond to its ecosystem needs, HEIs can be able to overcome the limitations associated to peripheral regions and would consequently contribute to regional development.

We conduct a case study on a medium-size public university in the South region of Spain, namely the University of Huelva. In this case study, we combine quantitative and qualitative analysis in order to be able to understand the university's engagement in its region. To do so, we need to profile the university, as well as to characterize the region as a peripheral region. Thus, we will be able to analyze the role that the university plays in regional development and how the peripheral condition of the region influences it. The design of research aims to contribute to the ongoing discussion regarding the role of universities in peripheral regions. Our contribution is twofold: on the one hand, we provide empirical evidence that helps to clarify the existing contradiction regarding the role of universities in peripheral regions. In this sense, the availability of further empirical evidence would lead to comparisons between regions and would contribute to identifying the factors that can enable the universities' societal contribution (Cai and Ahmad 2023, Compagnucci and Spigarelli 2020, Delbridge et al. 2025). Indeed, our results show that HEIs can contribute to peripheral regions as long as they are able to develop a regional profile that responds to the needs of the ecosystem. More concretely, our analysis shows the case of a university that contributes to its peripheral region because it has developed a regional profile characterised by a TM strategy that fits the Sustainable Entrepreneurial University model identified in the literature (Cai and Ahmad 2023) together with an orientation towards applied sciences and local impact (Siqueira et al. 2025; Bonaccorsi et al. 2023; Cai et al. 2025).

On the other hand, our case study focus on individual researchers instead on persons responsible for knowledge transfer policies at the level of the university (Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022) or desk-research (Kohoutek et al. 2017). By doing so we obtain a more grained perspective on the societal role of the university while responding to the calls in the literature for including scholars in the analysis and focusing on micro-practices from academics (Compagnucci and Spigarelli, 2020). Our results highlight the importance of personal networks and bottom-up experiences instead of top-down decisions and policies in shaping a HEI's regional profile.

2. Literature review: HEI's regional profile in peripheral regions

Peripheral regions are characterized by a lack of economic dynamism, low levels of absorptive capacity of firms, lack of innovative culture, low institutional density, worse technical and social infrastructures and older housing stock (Tödtling et al. 2011, Karlsen et al. 2017, Eder 2019, Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022). The characteristics of their innovation and industry fit those of “thin regional innovation systems”: several medium- and small- sized enterprises and a few larger, externally owned firms, few or no HEIs, and little knowledge exchange (Tödtling and Trippl 2005, Isaksen 2014, Karlsen et al. 2017).

The above-mentioned characteristics of peripheral regions have a negative impact upon the interaction between universities and companies (Kohoutek et al. 2017, Cai and Ahmad 2023). On the one hand, companies in peripheries would not be able to collaborate at the same level as bigger and more technological firms in dynamic ecosystems (Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022). On the other hand, universities in peripheral regions would also experience limitations such as lack of infrastructure or working overload of researchers, which would hinder their capacity to join business networks (Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022). Consequently, they tend to focus on local linkages, while universities with more resources and greater absorptive capacity would be involved in broader, interregional networks thus being able to connect with more diversified sources of knowledge (Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022, Huggins et al. 2008). Accordingly, companies with high absorptive capacity would rather cooperate with top-tier universities regardless of their geographical location, instead of universities located in peripheral regions which might experience difficulties attracting high profile research and teaching staff (Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022).

Consequently, in peripheral regions there would be a mismatch between the skills provided by the university and the productive specialization of the region (Kohoutek et al. 2017). Instead of developing a regional leadership role in their ecosystem, universities in peripheries would just take a role in providing traditional science and technology (Cinar 2019, Pugh 2017), education (Karlsen et al. 2017) or consulting (Cabelkova et al. 2017).

As it has been pointed out, a wide strand of the literature supports the idea that universities in peripheral regions experience barriers that undermine their societal role (Kohoutek et al. 2017, Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022, Cai and Ahmad 2023). Nevertheless, recent literature showcases HEIs that contribute importantly to their peripheral regions (Aranguren et al. 2016, Delbridge et al. 2025, Cai et al. 2025, Siqueira et al. 2025).

How can we understand this apparent contradiction? To answer this question, we suggest that HEIs contribution does not only depend on exogenous factors – such as its embeddedness in a peripheral region – but also on endogenous factors. We argue that HEIs in peripheral regions have to face limitations associated to thin regional innovation systems that can be a barrier for the collaboration with local companies (Kohoutek et al.

2017, Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022, Cai and Ahmad 2023). In order to avoid it, HEIs can develop a regional profile (Kohoutek et al. 2017) that responds to the needs of the regional ecosystem. In doing so, they adapt their orientation and their TM strategy – endogenous factors – to a context characterized by peripherality – exogenous factor. In the following lines we analyze these two aspects of HEI’s regional profile, namely TM strategy and orientation, to determine what are the characteristics of the regional profile that facilitate HEI’s regional contribution

2.1. Third mission strategy and the regional profile of HEIs

The concept of third mission comes along with the Entrepreneurial University Model as a response to the two missions developed by Humboldtian University, namely teaching and researching (Etzkowitz 2004, Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff 1998). Additionally, the Entrepreneurial University develops a societal role through the commercialization of academic research. Nevertheless, during the last years a broader understanding of HEIs’ societal role has emerged in academic and political field which points out that HEIs must play a broader role in social and cultural regional transformation (Trippel et al. 2015, Cai and Ahmad 2023). It has received attention in the literature under different conceptualizations – e.g., Sustainable Entrepreneurial University (Cai and Ahmad 2023), Civic University (Goddard and Vallance 2013, Goddard et al. 2016), ideas of university ecology (Wright 2016), Engaged University (Benneworth 2013), University 4.0 (Giesenbauer and Müller-Christ 2020) or Responsible University (Sorensen et al. 2019). Although these concepts have different features (for a detailed review, see Cai and Ahmad 2023), all of them agree on a renewed understanding of the third mission, going beyond the restrictive view that assimilates it to the commercialization of knowledge through spin-offs and patents licensing (Compagnucci and Spinarelli 2020, Guerrero et al. 2024) (Table 1). Although acknowledging the distinct features of the wide variety of concepts, we will refer to this new societal role of HEIs as Sustainable Entrepreneurial University (SEU), following the conceptualization developed by Cai and Ahmad (2023).

Table 1. Features of Entrepreneurial University vs Sustainable Entrepreneurial University

Spectrum category	Entrepreneurial University	Sustainable Entrepreneurial University
Teaching	Teaching on/off campus	Challenge-based education Transdisciplinary education
Research	Search for useful knowledge	Applied research (Siqueira et al. 2025) Addresses the challenge of sustainability (Cai and Ahmad 2023, Benneworth 2013)
Third mission	Innovation strategy to foster technology transfer Open to serve external society Mostly techno-economic innovation	From technology transfer to knowledge exchange (Cai et al. 2020) Serves the societal needs (Cai and Ahmad 2023) Wider understanding of innovation that includes Social Sciences and Humanities
Synergies among the		Co-creation of knowledge Dual models of education

three missions and ecosystem		New forms of teaching oriented to society: micro credentials, life-long learning
Organization	Interdisciplinarity to promote innovation TTO and incubators to promote knowledge transfer	Transdisciplinarity to promote innovation (interdisciplinarity+societal engagement) TTO as dynamic brokers that foster value creation and entrepreneurship (Siqueira et al. 2025) Researchers as network agents (Knudsen et al. 2021)
HEI's role in the society	Knowledge producer for technology transfer	Shaping a better future society (Shapiro 2005)

Source: Own elaboration from Cai and Ahmad (2023).

SEU comes along with a new understanding of HEIs' third mission that assumes that HEIs should play a more active and ambitious role in regional development (Knudsen et al. 2021, Guerrero et al. 2024). In this vein, HEIs are asked to collaborate with industry, government, and civil society to address societal needs such as sustainability (Goddard et al. 2013, Trencher et al. 2014, Compagnucci and Spinarelli 2020, Guerrero et al. 2023). Through fostering institutional changes, HEIs are expected to shape a better future society (Cai and Ahmad 2023). Therefore, they would not only improve regional competitiveness and attractiveness, but also become change agents in optimizing their regions, thus contributing to economic, social, cultural and environmental sustainability (Purcell et al. 2019, Cai and Ahmad 2023).

Under this view, three aspects of the TM strategy stand out as relevant for the regional profile of HEI's in peripheral regions. Firstly, HEIs collaboration with the ecosystem goes beyond knowledge generation and transfer and becomes *knowledge co-creation* (Trencher et al. 2014, Reichert 2019, Cai et al. 2020, Cai and Ahmad 2023). Indeed, in order to develop a societal contribution, research and education must respond to the environment's needs (Gunasekara 2006, Uyarra 2010). Consequently, new activities that have not be considered traditionally under the third mission are developed together with ecosystems stakeholders, such as micro-credentials, lifelong learning or continuous education, including off-campus and online teaching (Sivapalan et al. 2016, Smidova et al. 2017, Cai and Ahmad 2023).

In this vein, recent evidence demonstrates that, contrary to the traditional beliefs, the positive externalities for firms associated derived from education are relatively higher than those of research (Bonaccorsi et al. 2023). Furthermore, the effects of both research and education are complementary and depend on geographical distance (Bonaccorsi et al. 2023). Hence, through the engagement of new graduates, consultancy and other forms of collaboration that responds to their needs, HEIs contribute to the ecosystem even in peripheral regions (Bonaccorsi et al. 2023). We suggest that, when co-creation of knowledge is conducted, local firms in peripheral regions would be interested in collaborating with local universities – regardless of their research excellence – and conducting these innovative forms of teaching and research because they respond to their needs.

Indeed, *addressing ecosystem's needs* would be the second relevant aspect of a HEI's regional profile. HEIs would contribute to peripheral regions when they address regional needs under a wider understanding of innovation that goes beyond technology transfer by engaging Social Sciences and Humanities (Aranguren et al. 2016, Compagnucci and Spinarelli 2020, Dent et al. 2024, Riviezzo et al. 2025). Consequently, TM would promote transdisciplinary research that addresses HEIs' and ecosystem's common challenges (Compagnucci and Spinarelli 2020). Recent literature on innovation argues that previous literature focuses on an inappropriately narrowly framed concept of innovation (Shearmur 2015, Glückler et al. 2023, Castaldi 2024) and challenges the widespread belief that innovation activities are far more successful in large cities, showing that peripheral areas are also able to deliver innovation (Shearmur 2015, Eder 2019, Eder and Tripl 2019, Fritsch and Wyrwich 2021a, Pugh and Dubois 2021, Glückler et al. 2023, Castaldi 2024). They suggest that regions may present a path-dependent innovation specialization – not necessarily technological – that is intertwined with territorial properties or cultural assets (Castaldi 2024, Fritsch and Wyrwich 2021b).

Thirdly, HEIs' regional contribution depends on *HEI's role in the society*. In this sense, HEIs contribute when they support innovation strategies that advance the achievement of regional industrial and societal challenges (Tripl et al. 2015, Knudsen et al. 2021, Cai and Ahmad 2023). In order to achieve this societal role, HEIs transform their traditional structures and create new ones to strengthen the collaboration with the ecosystem (Cai and Ahmad 2023, Dent et al. 2024). For instance, research units also evolve into living labs and interdisciplinary research units that allow the co-creation of transdisciplinary knowledge and impact positively in regional development (Knudsen et al. 2021, Terconli and Jongbloed 2022, Canto-Farachala 2024). Finally, researchers themselves become network agents to attract and connect high-tech industries in the local systems of knowledge. In this vein, they often balance their role in HEIs with positions and activities in industry as workers or advisors (Knudsen et al. 2021, Dent et al. 2024, Planck et al. 2024).

Finally, at individual's level, HEI's regional contribution also depends on the recognition of regional engagement within the academic reward system (Sánchez-Barrioluengo and Benneworth 2019; Sormani et al. 2021). Thus, *institutional policy for knowledge transfer* can also influence researchers' propensity to engage in transfer activities as it determines how these activities are recognised within the academic reward system (Sormani et al. 2021). Moreover, HEI's TM strategy evolve in response to the societal role that HEIs are expected to play according to national and regional knowledge transfer policy. In this sense, it has been noted that TM structures that have been associated to the Entrepreneurial University model such as technology transfer offices (TTO) have been transformed to comply with the societal role of HEIs from simple intermediaries to dynamic brokers that foster value creation and entrepreneurship (Siqueira et al. 2025).

2.2. HEIs' orientation and regional profile

The literature about HEI's role in peripheral regions has also suggested that HEI's orientation may influence its regional contribution (Kohoutek et al. 2017). The orientation may include different dimensions (Cai et al. 2025). Firstly, HEIs can be classified according to their specialization focus, ranging from basic research to applied sciences. Kohoutek et al. (2017) identify three ideal-types of universities according to their orientation: classic research intensive, vocationally oriented teaching and research and vocationally oriented teaching focus. A fourth type is mentioned but not applied in their study, that is, technology-oriented universities (Kohoutek et al. 2017).

A second dimension in HEI's orientation is the trade-off between local impact and international scientific relevance (Cai et al. 2025). Both dimensions are related, as universities focused on basic research use to seek international scientific relevance, while universities that seeks local impact focus on applied sciences. Although the global and local dimensions are not inherently contradictory (Pinheiro and Abualrub 2021), the limited resources of universities impose the need for a strategy that defines their allocation (Cai et al. 2025).

Each alternative is ideally represented by one of the two models of universities that are present in Europe: on the one hand, universities of applied sciences (UAS), that conduct applied research and challenge-based education that aims to responds to the needs of their ecosystems; on the other hand, traditional research universities, that aims to increase their visibility and impact at the international level through high impact research that is measured by international rankings (RU).

A HEI's strategic orientation is path dependent and cannot be drastically changed (Kohoutek et al. 2017). In this sense, the creation of a university can be the outcome of a deliberate regional development policy or responds to the merger of institutions that already played a regional mission. Moreover, it also depends on the regions' needs (Benneworth 2018, Bonaccorsi et al. 2023, Cai et al. 2025). In this regard, it has been argued that, compared to their counterparts in central, urbanised areas with dense human and technical infrastructures, universities in more peripheral regions have been expected to contribute more to the development of their immediate geographies (Benneworth 2018). Universities in central locations often adopt a more global focus, prioritizing scientific excellence over local relevance (Cai et al. 2025). In this sense, the importance of an orientation to applied research has been highlighted in the literature (Siqueira et al. 2025). According to Bonaccorsi et al. (2023) "peripheral regions might benefit more from HEIs that specialize in applied research of interest to the local economy, not necessarily of international standards, while still producing large numbers of qualified and employable graduates" (Bonaccorsi et al. 2023).

2.3. HEI's regional profile as a response to peripherality

Based on the literature reviewed, we conceptualise the regional profile of HEIs as the result of the interaction between two endogenous dimensions: third mission strategy and institutional orientation. While peripherality constitutes an exogenous contextual condition, the regional profile developed by the institution shapes its societal role and forms of regional engagement. Figure 1 summarises the analytical framework adopted in this study.

Figure 1. Determinants of HEI's regional contribution

We suggest that a HEI's profile may evolve – although limited by its own path dependency – over time, in response to its context's characteristics. Therefore, we argue that HEI's regional contribution would depend on how HEI's regional profile evolve in response to the regional context, creating an evolutionary trajectory that is specific to each university. More concretely, we suggest that when a HEI's regional profile has evolved to respond to its ecosystem needs, HEIs can be able to overcome the limitations associated to peripheral regions and would consequently contribute to regional development.

3. Case presentation and results

3.1. Case presentation

We focus on the University of Huelva, a medium-sized higher education institution that was founded in 1997. It plays a central role in the economy and society of the region, the province of Huelva. In this sense, the university conducted an impact study in 2019 which concluded that it has a direct impact on sectors such as retail, hospitality, housing rentals, and professional services, making it a key pillar of economic activity in the city

(University of Huelva, 2019). Similarly, previous studies have highlighted the important role played by academic spin-off companies as mechanism to transfer knowledge from the University of Huelva to the local industry (Aceytuno and De Paz 2008).

The province of Huelva is located in the south-westernmost part of Spain. It is one of the nine provinces of Andalusia, an autonomous community in southern Spain. Huelva borders Portugal in the West, the autonomous community of Extremadura in the North and the Atlantic Ocean in the South.

Huelva covers 2% of Spain's territory and 11.56% of Andalusia, and the presence of protected natural areas is significant, with almost 30% of the territory under protection. The most notable of these is the Doñana National Park. With a population of 1,09% and 6.2% of the Spanish and Andalusian populations respectively, Huelva has a lower population density of 53.49 inhabitants per square kilometre, in contrast to 97.96 in Spain and 99.70 in Andalusia. Nevertheless, Huelva has a higher foreign population than Andalusia – 12.04% and 10.85% respectively – although this is lower than the Spanish average (14.61%).

The educational levels in Huelva are lower than the Spanish average. The percentage of the population in Huelva that has completed only primary school or lower secondary education is 48.79% and 33.61% respectively, while the averages for Spain are 46.33% and 30.95% respectively. Conversely, the percentages of the population that have completed upper secondary and post-secondary education are higher in Spain at 16.19% and 6.52% respectively, compared to 11.72% and 5.79% in Huelva. Similarly, Huelva ranks second among Spanish provinces for the rate of early school leavers, at 30.1% for men and 21.1% for women, compared to a Spanish average of 23.1% and 15.5%, respectively.

Huelva has a long-standing industrial character; industry accounts for 20.55% of the regional GDP, which is much higher than the Andalusian (10.9%) and Spanish (14.7%) averages. The province specialises in heavy industry, with a lower presence of manufacturing (5.83%, compared to 6.6% in Andalusia and 11.0% in Spain). The province is still tackling the environmental impact of this heavy industry, such as soil contamination and air pollution, mainly from mining and chemistry. Huelva is also specialised in agriculture, which represents 7.6% of its production, compared to 5.9% in Andalusia and 2.6% in Spain. This is intensive and export-oriented agriculture, mainly focused on strawberries and other red fruits, which attracts foreign labour force. It explains Huelva's important role in Spanish exports (it ranks 18th out of Spain's 50

provinces). Its specialisation in the export of raw materials results in a low economic complexity index of -0.78, placing it last among Spain's 50 provinces.¹

According to Nilsen et al.'s (2022) typology of peripheral regions, Huelva can be considered a 'locked-in' specialised region combining service centres, such as governmental structures and regional universities, which is typical of medium-sized regions, with a highly specialised industrial focus in just a few areas. Indeed, the economy of Huelva is based on the above-mentioned intensive agriculture in the coast, a heavy industrial pole focused on petrochemistry in the metropolitan area, copper mining in the Centre of the province and a very traditional and specialized agro-industry in the North.

In summary, the region presents the characteristics of peripheral regions or “places that don’t matter” (Rodríguez-Pose, 2018), such as depopulation, lower educational attainment, remoteness and organizational thinness (Eder 2019, Tödtling & Trippl, 2005, Nilsen et al. 2022).

3.2. Methodology

Our case study intends to respond to the research questions by characterizing the role that HEIs plays in the region, identifying both exogenous (regional peripherality) and endogenous (university’s profile) factors that determine its regional contribution. To do so, we focus on a HEI located in a peripheral region, the University of Huelva. Our case study combines quantitative and qualitative analyses. On the one hand, we conducted a quantitative analysis through a survey among researchers who have leaded technology transfer activities during 2025 – whether it is the creation of academic spin-offs or knowledge transfer contracts with local firms and institutions. On the other hand, the results of the questionnaire were complemented with interviews and the analysis of university documents and reports about the university and its region.

In order to identify the potential respondents of the questionnaire and the interviews, we use a database of 120 researchers who had engaged in knowledge transfer activities during 2025 provided by the Technology Transfer Office. The database was refined by deleting repetitions – researchers who engaged in more than one activities – and those who engaged in activities that cannot be purely considered knowledge transfer such as contracts with other universities to provide teaching. As a result, we obtained a database of 98 researchers who were contacted by email in the first week of January 2026. Reminders were sent by email twice after two weeks, obtaining 38 responses, that is 38,8% rate of response. To assess the potential for non-response bias, the characteristics of survey respondents (n = 38) were compared with those of the full sampling frame (N = 98). Comparisons were conducted across three key dimensions:

¹ <https://complejidadeconomica.cotec.es/informe/provincia/huelva>

scientific field, gender, and seniority level. The distribution of respondents closely mirrored that of the target population, with no substantial differences observed in any of these characteristics. This suggests that the respondent group is broadly representative of the wider population of researchers included in the study.

Table 2. Basic features of respondents

Distribution by sex	Male: 60,5 % Female: 39,5%
Distribution by age groups	<30: 10,5% 31-50: 15,8% 51-65: 71% >65: 2,6%
Distribution by scientific area	Arts and Humanities: 5,2% Health Sciences: 10,5% Natural Sciences: 13,1% Social Sciences: 42,1% Engineering: 28,9%
Distribution by transfer activity	Projects: 86,8% Academic spin-offs: 13,2%
Distribution by seniority	Junior (<5 years of experience): 13,2% Intermediate (5-15): 34,2% Expert (>15): 52,6%

As shown in Table 2, the typical researcher involved in knowledge transfer activities at the University of Huelva is a male researcher, between 51 and 65 years old with more than 15 years of experience. Projects are most used mechanism of knowledge transfer, and a great variety of scientific areas can be observed, although Social Sciences and Engineering are the most relevant ones.

Respondents were asked to answer a survey structured in three sections. The first part was devoted to the individual characteristics of the respondents, their motivation to engage in knowledge transfer, and their research and teaching profile. A second section was devoted to the University of Huelva's profile, as we asked our respondents to characterize the third mission conducted by the university and its orientation. Finally, we asked about characteristics of the knowledge transfer activity and its results, with special focus on the effects for the region. In total, the questionnaire was composed by 35 open and closed questions. A Likert scale from 1 to 5 was used for all the closed questions. From the responses obtained we build 9 dimensions of variables and the results are displayed in the following section.

In order to achieve a deeper understanding of the university's role in the region and characterizing its profile in deep, we also conducted semi-structured expert interviews (questionnaire and codesystem available in Zenodo in Authors, 2026). Semi-structured

interviews have been widely used to analyze the HEIs' contexts, given that they combine their theoretical applicability with methodological flexibility (Aceytuno et al. 2026). In the context of this study, the use of semi-structured interviews allows for the integration of the different aspects of a HEI's profile and, through "analytical generalisation" findings are transferable to theoretical propositions (Myers, 2019). We conducted 10 interviews to researchers who had engaged in third mission activities, as they have been directly involved in the social phenomenon under investigation and are thus a source of specialised, experience-based knowledge.

Interviews were conducted virtually via Microsoft Teams between April and May 2026. Transcripts were produced using Read.ai, an automated transcription tool. The interviews were conducted by the same researcher in order to guarantee standardisation. To increase reliability, we applied a double-checking process that involved collaborative segmentation, paraphrasing, and sub-coding. Data were analysed using qualitative content analysis through MaxQDA software, using a coding process that combined both deductive and inductive elements that was based on the literature review (Mayring 2014).

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Results from the quantitative analysis

From the responses obtained in our questionnaire we obtained a broad set of variables describing personal, professional, contextual, organizational, and relational characteristics of researchers involved in knowledge transfer, the university and the regional context. To reduce this complexity and identify analytically meaningful constructs, nine dimensions of variables were built to characterize the HEI's regional profile following the proposed theoretical framework. A reliability analysis was conducted using Cronbach's alpha for each proposed group of variables. Only clusters meeting a minimum threshold of $\alpha \geq 0.60$ were retained (see note in Table 3), following accepted standards for exploratory research. Table 3 summarizes the dimensions and the variables included in each of them.

Table 3. Dimensions

Dimension	Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Number of elements
<i>Influence of regional context</i>			
Peripherality	Huelva_lackdinamism Huelva_lackinnovativeculture Huelva_lackinfraestructure Huelva_lackinstitutionaldev Huelva_peripherality Huelva_mismatchskillsjobs	0,844	6

Institutional support for knowledge transfer (national and regional)	Factor_plannac Factor_polreg	0,739	2
Institutional support for knowledge transfer (local)	Publicsupport_diputacion Publicsupport_camaracomercio Publicsupport_asociacionempres Publicsupport_otros	0,609*	4
<i>HEI's regional profile</i>			
<i>HEI's orientation</i>			
University orientation towards international relevance	UHUinternac_acuerdos UHUinternac_movilidad UHUinternac_jointresearch UHUinternac_captación	0,894	4
University orientation towards local impact	UHU_basicresearch UHU_appliedsciences UHU_Engineering	0,657*	3
<i>HEI's TM strategy</i>			
University-industry cocreation of knowledge	Reltransf_investigdoc Reldocencia_ecosystem Relresearch_ecosystem	0,688*	3
Response to the ecosystem needs	Caract_respondneeds Caractert_Interdisciplinarity Caract_Openscience Satisfaccion_PDI Saatisfaccion_stakeholders Satisfaccion_owner Caract_citizenship Result_masdeloesperado Result_investig Result_aplicacionreal Result_utilidadsocial Result_utilidadpercibida Result_largoplazo Caract_betterfuture	0,883	14
Societal role of the university	UHUas_knowledgecocreator UHUas_trustcreator UHUas_interdisciplinarity UHUas_betterfuture UHUas_dialogue UHUas_developmentcoord	0,825	6
Institutional support for knowledge transfer (university)	OTRI_encagent OTRI_partnercontact OTRI_tecsupport OTRI_legalsupport Catedras_asfactor Factor_polUHU	0,871	6

(*) Three dimensions fall below the conventional 0.70 threshold ($\alpha = 0.609, 0.657, 0.688$). We apply ≥ 0.60 'exploratory' cut-off i

The first retained dimension, peripherality, captures structural territorial constraints derived from the peripheral nature of the region, such as lack of dynamism, innovative culture, infrastructure, and low institutional development. The influence of the context is completed with two additional dimensions capturing the influence of knowledge transfer policy at national, regional and local. Regarding the HEI's regional profile, a first set of dimensions capture its orientation towards international relevance and local impact respectively. The remaining dimensions characterize the TM strategy developed at the university in relation to the main characteristics of SEU model – societal role, cocreation of knowledge together with the ecosystem and university responding to the ecosystem needs – as well as the policy implemented at the university level to promote knowledge transfer. A Friedman test was conducted to evaluate whether the distributions of the measures differ; the results confirm that its null can be rejected .

Table 4. Results of the Friedman test

Test	N	χ^2	df	p-value
Friedman test	38	156,63	8	<0,001

Post hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted using Bonferroni correction to control for Type I error. The adjusted results revealed a structured pattern of significant differences. At the lower end, knowledge transfer policies-local showed significantly lower scores than most other dimensions, including Institutional support for knowledge transfer - university ($p = .045$), Orientation towards local impact ($p = .001$), Peripherality ($p < .001$), Societal role ($p < .001$), Response to the ecosystem needs ($p < .001$), and University-industry co-creation of knowledge ($p < .001$). Similarly, the Orientation towards international relevance was significantly lower than several dimensions, including Orientation towards local impact ($p = .014$), Peripherality ($p = .004$), Societal role ($p < .001$), Response to the ecosystem needs ($p < .001$), and Co-creation ($p < .001$). Dimensions related to Institutional support for knowledge transfer also showed differences: national and regional level and University level scored significantly lower than Societal role, Response to ecosystem needs, and Co-creation (all $p \leq .002$). In contrast, the highest-ranked dimensions – Co-creation, Response to ecosystem needs, and Societal role—did not significantly differ from each other (all adjusted $p = 1.000$), forming a statistically homogeneous high-performing block.

Table 5. Bonferroni-adjusted pairwise comparisons. Only statistically significant differences ($p < .05$) are reported.

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
University-industry co-creation of knowledge	7.49

Response to the ecosystem needs	7.46
Societal role of the university	6.88
Peripherality	5.16
University orientation towards local impact	4.96
Institutional support for knowledge transfer (university)	4.36
Institutional support for knowledge transfer (national/regional)	3.63
University orientation towards international relevance	2.74
Institutional support for knowledge transfer (local)	2.33

Overall, the results suggest the existence of three differentiated clusters: (1) a high-scoring group centred on the characteristics of SEU model of TM strategy such as co-creation, responding to the ecosystem needs and societal engagement; (2) an intermediate group related to the university's orientation towards local impact and responding to ecosystem's needs and the impact of regional context (peripherality); and (3) a low-scoring group associated with the university's international scientific relevance and the institutional support for knowledge transfer conducted at national, regional and local level. These results show that the regional profile of the University of Huelva is characterized by (1) an orientation towards local impact instead of international relevance; (2) a TM strategy aligned to the characteristics of the SEU model; and (3) is highly determined by the peripherality of the region.

3.3.2. Results from the qualitative analysis

Based on empirical data from ten interviews with researchers experienced in knowledge transfer, we find support to the results obtained from the quantitative analysis. Furthermore, they bring about additional aspects regarding the university's regional profile and how it relates to the peripherality of the region. The following lines present our findings in detail².

All the interviewees agree on the peripherality of the region of Huelva and that it has an impact on their transfer activities. Nevertheless, instead of reporting a negative effect of the characteristics of the region, most of them consider it to be an opportunity. Indeed, they consider that the relative geographical isolation of the university can be seen as an opportunity for the university to play a more relevant role in its ecosystem. They compare it to the situation of other HEIs in central locations which have to compete with other HEI's and institutions to collaborate with the industry. On the contrary, they think that the University of Huelva is, a priori, on an advantageous position regarding knowledge transfer if compared to HEIs in central regions. Moreover, personal ties and mutual

² Extracts from interviews have been translated from the originals in Spanish using Deepl.com and translation quality was controlled by the authors.

knowledge are more frequent in small cities like Huelva, which is reported also as a facilitator of knowledge exchanges.

Nevertheless, three of the interviewees agree one obstacle to their transfer activities related to the peripherality of the region, namely, the fact that some industrial companies located in Huelva are part of big national and multinational companies whose decision centres are located in Madrid or Sevilla. This has two consequences for the transfer activities: on the one hand, these companies tend to collaborate with universities in these central cities; consequently, the university has to focus more on small local companies on the other hand, even when they are able to collaborate with the university of Huelva, there can be obstacles and barriers for the project to be successful:

What's the problem? It's that we little ones [...] have the resources we have. [...] Large universities with established groups have far more success stories with big companies. Let me give you a specific example, take a look. We're a group of [...], the only one at the University of Huelva. However, we can't measure up; we don't have the capacity to compete with the [...] group at the University of Seville. In other words, that group has been established for many years before we started working on very similar things, because the work we do is very similar, yet they have project know-how with Endesa, with Iberdrola, with the big companies; and, as they are very happy with the results those universities provide, they don't even think about changing. So, what is our relationship as a group with the large companies we have here in Huelva? Well, the only relationship we have is asking for support for a project we propose or for them to ask us for good students to hire, do you see? The possibility of knowledge transfer is minimal. How do we go about it? Well, we look elsewhere, because we know that even though there's a [name of large company] here, the head office in Seville is in charge and already has its contracts with Seville. (Interview 4).

It's true that many of the people currently working in the chemical cluster were once my students, so I don't know if that happens elsewhere; perhaps it's a positive thing in the sense that, for example, I'm currently supervising a PhD thesis for a manager at one of the cluster's factories. On the negative side, unfortunately [...] decision-making centres are now in Madrid, so you might have initiatives and so on; for example, not long ago—well, about a year or so ago—I published a very good article in a top-tier journal containing data from [a technology transfer project]. And what happened? It was an absolute nightmare, a nightmare, I tell you, getting authorisation to use the data, wasn't it? Yes. So, in the end I had to speak to a factory manager who'd been in Huelva five years ago and whom I did know because, well, due to circumstances I had a connection with him and it was made easier for me, but the decision-making centre isn't in Huelva now; the people at the factory have very limited power because of the headquarters, which

are in Madrid. So, in that respect, I do think it does have an influence, but on the positive side, many students go straight to the industrial park to do their work placements and there's a very strong interaction between the industrial sector and the university; and on the negative side, decisions are currently taken outside of... So they're taken in Madrid, aren't they? (Interview 1).

Regarding the regional profile of the university, our respondents agree on perceiving it as the outcome of an evolutionary process. In this sense, several interviewees highlight that the university's role in the territory has evolved since the creation of the university as a response to the ecosystem's needs. Very interestingly, endogenous factors such as the promotion policy implemented by the university, do not seem to be relevant according to our respondents. On the contrary, they suggest that the regional profile of the university has evolved through a process that has not been directed or guided by the university's mission or strategic direction, but is rather the result of the researchers' own independent efforts. In this sense, when asked about their motivations to conduct transfer activities, our respondents talk either about their passion for knowledge transfer or the ecosystem needs, and suggest that until recently the academic system did not recognise enough knowledge activities:

Well, I'd say that in the past, knowledge transfer wasn't valued at all. Of course, it wasn't done... I mean, now it's become fashionable and that transfer is a priority. So, naturally, the way we perceive it now is that I believe there's a much stronger development of these knowledge transfer processes from our university to industry, isn't there? (Interview 2).

Our respondents identify the characteristics of the SEU model in the TM strategy conducted at the University of Huelva. In this sense, they agree on the importance of interdisciplinarity – crucial to address the complexity of societal problems:

The same applies to environmental issues: you have to bring different people together so that everyone can give their opinion, because these are like systems where, if you make a change—according to general systems theory—it has an impact. Systems engineering is a method for solving complex problems, and that's exactly what it is: you make a change that appears to be optimal from the system's point of view, but it affects other systems, so a multidisciplinary approach is required (Interview 4).

Moreover, there is a wide agreement about the understanding of the TM as a response to societal needs. In this sense, they acknowledge that their final goal is contributing to building a better future for Huelva, with important references to sustainability; and, very interestingly, our respondents highlight, the knowledge cocreation process between

ecosystem and university and interrelationships between teaching, researching and transfer:

I can assure you that the co-creation of new knowledge stems not only from what we as teachers know, but also from what we hear from those who deal with the factory's day-to-day problems [...] They play a major part; they are the ones who provide us with insights, and sometimes they come up with ideas that we would never have thought of ourselves (Interview 2).

When you approach a company to take on a project, the company already has expertise that predates your involvement. In other words, they know—above all, they know how the system they want to improve works, and they know what they want to do to improve it. That knowledge is essential for us to start working on it. And then, as we work and see opportunities to improve whatever it is, we have to discuss it with them, because they're the ones who'll eventually bring it to market, and sometimes they'll tell us themselves: 'Not this way, that way,' or 'Hey, look, this is better – I'm interested in this even if I'm not going to bring it to market.' Of course, and there always has to be that co-creation you're talking about; it's essential in contracts, always (Interview 4).

Finally, our respondents also highlight the importance of personal contacts and ties between the university and the ecosystem. In this sense, they consider to be far more important than the promotion policy implemented by the university. These personal contacts provide trust, which is key in the decision of the company/institution to collaborate with the university:

I mean, if that person has worked with someone from XX University, and knows that it works well, that they get on, that they speak the same language, why would they change? I wouldn't do it either. Unless I was looking for something very specific that only someone at another university could provide. But of course, given that universities adapt to what companies want, that's very unlikely to happen. [...] And besides, [that trust] is inherited, because the person the company initially contacted might retire, but the trust remains because there has already been contact with their colleagues who are still working on the same thing and have worked as a team (Interview 4).

4. Discussion

Our theoretical framework suggests that HEIs develop their societal contribution according to both exogenous and endogenous factors. On the one hand, university's regional profile – determined by its orientation and TM strategy – endogenously determines its societal role; on the other hand, this societal role is also a response to the

local context and the needs of the regional stakeholders (Compagnucci and Spigarelli 2020, Göransson et al. 2009); therefore, the characteristics of the ecosystem – peripherality – will be an exogenous factor influencing HEIs' societal role.

Our theoretical model highlights five aspects of a HEI's regional profile, four of them related to the TM strategy and one related to the HEI's institutional orientation. Focusing on the first group, the results of our case study show that the third mission strategy goes beyond the commercialization of academic research; indeed, the third mission strategy pictured by our respondents aligns with the Sustainable Entrepreneurial University that assumes that HEIs should play a more active and ambitious role in regional development (Knudsen et al. 2021, Guerrero et al. 2024). Indeed, our results show the importance of knowledge co-creation between HEI and ecosystem that goes beyond the third mission by creating linkages between teaching, research and knowledge transfer (Trencher et al. 2014, Reichert 2019, Cai et al. 2020, Cai and Ahmad 2023). As several respondents indicate, activities from first and second missions are developed together with ecosystems stakeholders, who participates in teaching as well as research and, consequently, develop research and education that also respond to the environment's needs (Gunasekara 2006, Uyarra 2010).

Furthermore, the third mission strategy is also characterized by its interdisciplinarity. It goes beyond the traditional technological dimension and acknowledges the importance of Social Sciences and Humanities (Aranguren et al. 2016, Compagnucci and Spigarelli 2020, Dent et al. 2024, Riviezzo et al. 2025). We suggest that the important degree of interdisciplinarity that our case study shows, with a remarkable participation of Social Sciences and Humanities, shows how HEIs can contribute to regional innovation needs from a wider perspective that goes beyond technology transfer. Our results also provide support to the idea that peripheral areas are also able to deliver innovation (Shearmur 2015, Eder 2019, Eder and Trippel 2019, Fritsch and Wyrwich 2021a, Pugh and Dubois 2021, Glückler et al. 2023, Castaldi 2024) going thus beyond the inappropriately narrowly framed concept of innovation (Shearmur 2015, Glückler et al. 2023, Castaldi 2024) that has traditionally been used in the literature.

Following this strategy, the university that has been analysed has been capable of playing an active role in economic and social development and, to do so, they support innovation strategies that advance the achievement of regional industrial and societal challenges (Trippel et al. 2015, Knudsen et al. 2021, Cai and Ahmad 2023). Instead of developing univocal collaborations with industry to transfer knowledge, the university has become an agent that builds trust among the diverse actors in the ecosystems (Cai and Ahmad 2023), thus developing an active role in engaging and supporting strategic innovation activities in its peripheral region (Delbridge et al. 2025).

The societal contribution of the University of Huelva is determined by the fact that the university responds to the needs of local companies and institutions. As indicated in the

literature, through the engagement of new graduates, consultancy and other forms of collaboration that responds to their needs, it contributes to the ecosystem regardless of the limitations present in peripheral regions (Bonaccorsi et al. 2023) which are acknowledged by the researchers but not necessarily as limitations; on the contrary, they show that even if some characteristics of the region – such as the lack of infrastructures or dynamism – may not facilitate knowledge transfer, they consider that other may constitute opportunities such as the lack of strong companies that eventually create an opportunity for creating academic spin-offs. Again, it depends on whether the university is capable or not to respond to the needs of its ecosystem.

As it was argued in the theoretical framework, HEI's societal contribution would be the response to these factors that jointly influence each other, creating an evolutionary trajectory that is specific to each university. Arguably, when a HEI's societal role has evolved to respond to its ecosystem needs, HEIs can be able to overcome the limitations associated to peripheral regions and would consequently contribute to regional development. In our case study, although the TM strategy has evolved as a response to the environmental needs, it's not that clear that the university's orientation has done the same.

In this sense, the literature indicates that HEIs that contribute regional development transform their traditional structures and create new ones to strengthen the collaboration with the ecosystem (Cai and Ahmad 2023, Dent et al. 2024). For instance, technology transfer offices (TTO) transform themselves from simple intermediaries to dynamic brokers that foster value creation and entrepreneurship (Siqueira et al. 2025), while research units also evolve into living labs and interdisciplinary research units that allow the co-creation of transdisciplinary knowledge and impact positively in regional development (Knudsen et al. 2021, Terconli and Jongbloed 2022, Canto-Farachala 2024). Nevertheless, according to our results, this transformation has not happened in our case study. On the contrary, our respondents report the lack of impact of the university's policies and supporting structures.

We suggest that the reason behind this fact is the mixed orientation of the university, that combines its focus on local impact and applied sciences with the features of a generalist university. Although the global and local dimensions are not inherently contradictory (Pinheiro and Abualrub 2021), the limited resources of universities impose the need for a strategy that defines their allocation (Cai et al. 2025). Nevertheless, institutional factors may limit a HEI's capacity to do so; on the one hand, applied sciences universities do not exist in the context of our case study; on the other hand, a HEI's strategic orientation is path dependent and cannot be drastically changed (Kohoutek et al. 2017). In this sense, our case study show that a university today is the result of a complex evolutionary process and, even if its orientation might not be ideal, reverting it is definitely not be possible. Besides, our results show that there would be no need for it,

given that the university's orientation has also evolved in response to the regions' needs (Benneworth 2018, Bonaccorsi et al. 2023, Cai et al. 2025). In this regard, researchers themselves have become network agents to attract and connect industries in the local systems of knowledge (Knudsen et al. 2021, Dent et al. 2024, Planck et al. 2024). They have developed an orientation towards applied sciences, regardless of the "official" orientation of the university and through it they effectively contribute to the regional development (Siqueira et al. 2025; Bonaccorsi et al. 2023).

This result is specially remarkable as it opens the discussion about the researcher agency and its role in shaping university's regional engagement from below. In this sense, researcher agency can be conceptualised as the capacity of individual researchers to initiate, shape and sustain university–region interactions through their own motivations, professional networks and engagement practices, independently of formal institutional strategies. According to our results, researcher agency can become a critical mechanism connecting universities and regional actors in peripheral regions, where institutional thickness is limited (Tödtling and Trippl 2005).

In summary, we find that a HEI's societal contribution can rather be the result of an evolutionary response to the environment's needs instead of the result of a decided policy designed by the university or any other local or regional institution. In these sense, endogenous factors – HEI's regional profile – evolve in response to exogenous factor – peripherality. Nevertheless, in our case study this process of transformation is rather the result of a spontaneous response by researchers seeking to adapt to the needs of the local community than a policy directed by the university authorities. Therefore, our results show that an effective knowledge transfer can be a bottom-up process driven by researchers through their personal contacts and networks with local institutions which have been built on previous experiences. Moreover, our results highlight the importance of personal networks and bottom-up experiences, that seem to be more important than top-down approaches and policies in building a HEI's regional profile that responds to peripherality.

5. Conclusions, policy implications and limitations and future lines of research

Our paper has focused on HEI's societal contribution with the objective of adding empirical evidence that helps to overcome the contradictions in the literature regarding the role that HEIs can play in peripheral regions. Building on previous literature (Cai and Ahmad 2023; Kohoutek et al. 2017) we argue that HEI's strategic approach to the TM is as a path-dependent trajectory which allows them to contribute to the development of peripheral regions. In this sense, HEIs develop a regional profile from endogenous factors – namely HEI's orientation and TM strategy – that evolve in response to an exogenous factor – peripherality.

Our paper realizes two main contributions. On the one hand, it contributes to the literature on HEI's societal role by providing new empirical evidence that helps to overcome the contradictions present in the literature about the role of HEIs in peripheral regions. In this sense, we demonstrate that HEIs can contribute to peripheral regions as long as they are able to develop a regional profile that responds to the needs of the ecosystem. More concretely, our analysis shows the case of a university that contributes to its peripheral region by developing a regional profile characterised by knowledge co-creation, orientation towards ecosystem needs, an active societal role and an institutional orientation towards applied sciences and local impact.

These results reinforces the idea found in the literature that TM strategy must avoid isomorphism, that is, the "star player syndrome" and the one-fits-all approach (Compagnucci and Spigarelli 2020). In our case study, the university has been able to develop a regional profile from below, following an evolutionary bottom-up process by means of which it has matched the specialization of its territory, thus becoming an agent that is complementary to the specificities of this peripheral region. Consequently, the university is able to find and exploit the opportunities for innovation that are present in its peripheral ecosystem. These results are in line with the recent literature about innovation in peripheral regions that suggest that they present a path-dependent innovation specialization – not necessarily technological – that is intertwined with territorial properties or cultural assets (Castaldi 2024, Fritsch and Wyrwich 2021b). In this context, HEIs that have evolved to become part of the path-dependent regional innovation specialization would contribute to its development.

Our paper also realizes a methodological contribution. In this sense, our case study includes a survey directed to individual researchers of the university who have been undertaking a responsible role in TM activity. Contrastingly, case studies in the literature tend to focus on persons responsible for knowledge transfer policies at the level of the university (Aparecido-Tomaz et al. 2022) or desk-research (Kohoutek et al. 2017). We consider that the information gathered at the individual level provides a more grained perspective on the societal role of the university – that is, the relationships between the university and its ecosystem and how peripherality may influence them. With our methodology we also respond to the calls in the literature for including scholars in the analysis and focusing on micro-practices from academics (Compagnucci and Spigarelli, 2020).

Finally, and partly because of this methodological contribution, our results highlight the importance of researcher agency by showing how personal networks and bottom-up experiences can be more relevant in shaping a HEI's regional profile instead of top-down decisions and policies. These results aligns with previous literature that highlights the possibility of mismatch between HEIs' capabilities and ecosystem's needs when specialization decisions respond to a top-down approach (Cabelkova et al. 2017).

Nevertheless, a regional profile that perfectly responds to the ecosystem's needs can also have a dark side: the literature also shows that, while regional universities or university colleges in specialised regions can support existing industries and be seen as facilitators of change, they can also contribute to the further specialisation of these regions (Nilsen et al., 2022). In this sense, the potential of top-down initiatives to diversify this limited specialisation, particularly in locked-in specialised regions, could be discussed. Therefore, further empirical evidence would clarify the importance of bottom-up and top-down actions in shaping a higher education institution's (HEI) regional profile.

References

Aceytuno, M.T. and De Paz, M.A. (2008): La creación de spin-off universitarias. El caso de la Universidad de Huelva. *Economía industrial*, 368, 97-111. <https://www.mintur.gob.es/Publicaciones/Publicacionesperiodicas/EconomiaIndustrial/RevistaEconomiaIndustrial/368/97.pdf>

Aparecido-Tomaz, P., Fischer, B., Meissner, D., & Rücker Schaeffer, P. (2022). The Dynamics of University-Industry Interactions in Peripheral Contexts: Evidence from Brazil. *Foresight and STI Governance*, 16(4), 59-69. <https://doi.org/10.17323/2500-2597.2022.4.59.69>

Aranguren, M. J., Guibert, J. M., Valdaliso, J. M., & Wilson, J. R. (2016). Academic Institutions as Change Agents for Territorial Development. *Industry and Higher Education*, 30(1), 27-40. <https://doi.org/10.5367/ihe.2016.0289>

Benneworth, P. (2013). *University Engagement with Socially Excluded Communities*, Springer.

Benneworth, P. (2018). *Universities and Regional Economic Development: Engaging with the Periphery*, Routledge, London. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315168357>

Bonaccorsi, A., Barin, L., Belingheri, P. et al. (2023). Is higher education more important for firms than research? Disentangling university spillovers, *The Journal of Technology Transfer* 49, 900-925. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-023-10008-y>

Cai, Y. & Ahmad, I. (2023), From an Entrepreneurial University to a Sustainable Entrepreneurial University: Conceptualization and Evidence in the Contexts of European University Reforms, *Higher Education Policy* 36(1), 20–52.

Cai, Y., Ma, J., & Chen, Q. (2020). Higher Education in Innovation Ecosystems. *Sustainability*, 12(11), 4376. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114376>

Cai, Y., Pinheiro, R., Cristofolletti, E.C. *et al.* Entrepreneurialism Meets Sustainability: Exploring Tensions in the Transition to Sustainable Entrepreneurial Universities. *Minerva* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-025-09597-9>

Canto-Farachala, P., Smith, M., Wise, E., & Johnson, M. P. (2024). Engaging for Sustainable Development and Transformation – Exploring the Concept of Transformative Academic Institutions. *Triple Helix*, 11(1), 75-106. <https://doi.org/10.1163/21971927-bja10049>

Castaldi, C. (2024). The geography of urban innovation beyond patents only: New evidence on large and secondary cities in the United States. *Urban Studies*, 61(7), 1248-1272. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00420980231204718>.

Compagnucci, L. & Spigarelli, F. (2020). The Third Mission of the university: A systematic literature review on potentials and constraints, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 161, 120284, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120284>

Delbridge, R., Henderson, D. & Morgan, K. (2025). *Innovating innovation in the periphery: new roles for universities and public actors*. Innovations in innovation policy, Cardiff University. Available online: <https://orca.cardiff.ac.uk/id/eprint/176871/1/Delbridge%20et%20al%202025%20Innovating%20innovation%20in%20the%20periphery.pdf>

Dent, T., England, L., & Comunian, R. (2023). The challenges of developing sustainable cultural and creative ecosystems and the role of higher education institutions: Lessons from Dundee and Chatham, UK. *Industry and Higher Education*, 38(1), 40-50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09504222231186367>

Eder J, Tripp M. Innovation in the periphery: Compensation and exploitation strategies. *Growth and Change*. 2019; 50: 1511–1531. <https://doi.org/10.1111/grow.12328>

Etzkowitz, H. (2004). The evolution of the entrepreneurial university. *International Journal of Technology and Globalisation*, 1(1), 64–77. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTG.2004.004551>,

Etzkowitz, H., & Leydesdorff, L. (1998). A Triple Helix of University–Industry–Government Relations: Introduction. *Industry and Higher Education*, 12(4), 197–201.

Fritsch M., Wyrwich M (2021b). Does Successful Innovation Require Large Urban Areas? Germany as a Counterexample. *Economic Geography*, 97 (3), pp. 284 - 308, Cited 43 times. DOI: 10.1080/00130095.2021.1920391

Fritsch M., Wyrwich M. (2021a). Is innovation (increasingly) concentrated in large cities? An international comparison. *Research Policy*, 50 (6), 104237. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2021.104237

Giesenbauer, B., & Müller-Christ, G. (2020). University 4.0: Promoting the Transformation of Higher Education Institutions toward Sustainable Development. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3371. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083371>

Goddard, J., Kempton, L., & Vallance, P. (2013). Universities and smart specialisation: Challenges, tensions and opportunities for the innovation strategies of European regions. *Ekonomiaz*, 83(2), 82–101.

Guerrero, M., Fayolle, A., Di Guardo, M. C., Lamine, W., & Mian, S. (2024). Re-viewing the entrepreneurial university: Strategic challenges and theory building opportunities. *Small Business Economics*, 63(2), 527–548. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-023-00858-z>

Gunasekara, C. (2006). Reframing the role of universities in the development of regional innovation systems. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 31(1), 101–113. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-005-5016-4>,

Isaksen, A. (2014). Industrial development in thin regions: Trapped in path extension? *Journal of Economic Geography*, 15(3), 585–600. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jeg/lbu026>

Glückler, J., Shearmur, R., Martinus, K. (2023). Liability or opportunity? Reconceptualizing the periphery and its role in innovation, *Journal of Economic Geography*, 23(1), 231–249, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jeg/lbac028>

Knudsen, M. P., Frederiksen, M. H., & Goduscheit, R. C. (2021). New forms of engagement in third mission activities: a multi-level university-centric approach. *Innovation*, 23(2), 209-240. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14479338.2019.1670666>

Knudsen, M. P., Frederiksen, M. H., & Goduscheit, R. C. (2021). New forms of engagement in third mission activities: a multi-level university-centric approach. *Innovation*, 23(2), 209-240. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14479338.2019.1670666>

Kohoutek, J., Pinheiro, R., Čábelková, I., & Šmídová, M. (2017). Higher education institutions in peripheral regions: A literature review and framework of analysis. *Higher Education Policy*, 30(4), 405–423. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41307-017-0062-8>

Mayring, P. (2014). *Qualitative content analysis: Theoretical foundation, basic procedures and software solution*. Klagenfurt, Austria. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-395173>

Nilsen, T., Grillitsch, M., & Hauge, A. (2023). Varieties of periphery and local agency in regional development. *Regional Studies*, 57(4), 749–762. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2022.2106364>

Pinheiro, R., Karlsen, J., Kohoutek, J., & Young, M. R. (2017). Universities' Third Mission: Global Discourses and National Imperatives. *Higher Education Policy*, 30(4), 425–442. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41307-017-0057-5>

Planck, S., Tomasi, S., Maisch, B., Henry, C., Gabriel, B., Singer, S., Skica, T., & Stoeckmann, C. (2025). Introduction. A New Social Contract for Higher Education Institutions: Exploring the Role of HEIs in European Innovation Ecosystems. *Triple Helix*, 11(3), 245-257. <https://doi.org/10.1163/21971927-12340020>

Pugh, R. (2017). Universities and economic development in lagging regions: 'Triple Helix' policy in Wales. *Regional Studies*, 51(7), 982–993. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2016.1171306>

Reichart, S. (2019). The role of universities in regional innovation ecosystems. European Universities Association, EUA, Brussels.

Riviezzo, A., Mason, M.C., Zamparo, G. *et al.* University in downtown: developing a new scale to assess the impact of university activities on the community. *J Technol Transf* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-025-10197-8>

Rodríguez-Pose, A. (2018). The revenge of the places that don't matter (and what to do about it). *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 11(1), 189–209. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjres/rsx024>

Sanchez-Barrioluengo, M. and Benneworth, P. (2019). Is the entrepreneurial university also regionally engaged? Analysing the influence of university's structural configuration on third mission performance, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 141, 2019, 206-218, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.10.017>.

Shearmur, R. (2015). Far from the madding crowd: Slow innovators, information value, and the geography of innovation. *Growth and Change*, 46(3), 424–442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/grow.12097>

Siqueira, E., Bin, A. & Brandão Fischer, B. Technology transfer as an enabler for the emergence of sustainable entrepreneurial universities. *J Technol Transf* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-025-10236-4>

Smidova, M., Smidova, O., Kyllingstad, N. & Karlsen, J. (2017). Regional development: Lifelong learning as a priority in Norway and the Czech Republic? *Higher Education Policy* 30, 499-516.

Sormani, E., Baaken, T., & van der Sijde, P. (2022). What sparks academic engagement with society? A comparison of incentives appealing to motives. *Industry and Higher Education*, 36(1), 19–36. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950422221994062>

Tercanli, H., & Jongbloed, B. (2022). A Systematic Review of the Literature on Living Labs in Higher Education Institutions: Potentials and Constraints. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12234. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912234>

Tödting, F., & Tripl, M. (2005). One size fits all? Towards a differentiated regional innovation policy approach. *Research Policy*, 34(8), 1203–1219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2005.01.018>

Tripl, M., Grillitsch, M., & Isaksen, A. (2015). *External “energy” for regional industrial change: Attraction and absorption of non-local knowledge for new path development*. Papers in Innovation Studies, No. 2015/47, Lund University.

University of Huelva (2019): Evaluación del impacto social, cultural y económico de la universidad de Huelva en su provincia, Consejo Económico y Social, 2019. <https://consejosandalucia.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Estudio-Impacto-UHU.pdf>

Uyarra, E. (2010). *Conceptualizing the regional roles of universities: Implications and contradictions*. *European Planning Studies*, 18(8), 1227–1246. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654311003791275>